

Leibniz-Junior Research Group

Urban human-nature resonance for sustainability transformation

Leibniz Institute of Ecological Urban and Regional Development (IOER)

URBNANCE Blog

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Essay 22, Mai 2025

The world as it confronts children as resonant beings, and the words

they choose for their discoveries.

“Bagger, Bagger, Bagger!” ...“Autoo, Auto, Auto”.. I hear my child shouting while I am riding with him on my bike to the kindergarten. Every day we get swallowed by the vibrant and loud city and whenever he sees an excavator, he points towards it with his cute little fingers making me aware of his discovery. He has a similar, but not that dominant fondness of cars. And the other day, I even caught myself thinking “Bagger!” while looking out the window of my office, turning to the construction site on the street across, apparently getting infected by this excavator madness. My son is almost two years old now, and talking becomes a reality day by day. I now have the privilege of getting to know word by word how the world seems to confront him. I am thereby wondering how he decides on what words are important to him. Is it a mere coincidence? Do those words have a specific practical meaning to him? Do they reveal his greatest interests? Or, is it a mixture of everything depending on what surrounds and confronts him regularly. Is it thus connected to his direct material environment in the city? Or is it mostly about his social environment: the people, his family, his parents, and “friends”? I am wondering about his choice of words, because if I am being honest, I wait for words that show a greater interest maybe in nature? When we leave the busy streets on our way to the kindergarten and driving through a big park, I am thus pointing towards what surrounds us saying things like “Uh, look a tree, some flowers, can you hear the birds?”. And just this morning, they started working in the park on a pathway with, you guessed it, an excavator, and there he goes again “Baagger, Bagger, Bagger”.

“Bagger, Bagger, Bagger!” (Picture: Mabel Ramisch)

Children as resonant beings

I am mostly curious, not really worried, but if I think about terms like [“nature-deficit disorder”](#) of urban citizens or about the general discourse about [nature disconnection](#) and

[relational crises](#) in sustainability science, I get perhaps a little worried after all? As [Hartmut Rosa](#) said: “The first and fundamental organ through which we enter into a responsive relationship with the world and make the world respond to us (...) is the voice” (p. 63). Thinking around some corners here: does that mean, that if my child focuses on things that represent machines of highly industrialized and accelerated societies, connecting to nature is in danger? That would be way too easy of a conclusion and certainly not true. What the German sociologist Rosa wants to show by granting the voice such fundamental power is, that children are experts, they are ‘beings of resonance’ by simply indulging in the relational back and forth of calling and being called by the world. Rosas’ theory of resonance is a term for a responsive and affective way of relating to the world as it confronts us. Resonance thereby presents as a counter term for mute relationships “modern” societies cultivate, where we are not touched anymore by what surrounds us. The excavator here being the object that calls to my child, does thus not necessarily lead to the manifestation of an anthropocentric worldview. It simply shows that he “cannot help but experiencing the world as responsive” (p. 362). The excavators and cars being very dominant words and things that inspired this text, however, have certainly not been his first chosen words to respond to the world.

Incorporating world through words

As many children, my son’s first word was Mama and I loved everything about that. His second word was Papa and his third word was Amos – our dog. It is not surprising to me, that he started saying Mama first. The relationship between mother and child usually already starts in the womb where the child has no idea that there is a separation of them and the world. [They feel and conceive everything as one](#). By entering the world however, what Rosa describes as a resonance shock, the voice and then of course also later specific words, become this incredible tool to make themselves heard and to make themselves as part of the world while being a subject of individuality and distinction. Seeking for basic needs such as physical contact and food, Mama becomes a very important word, especially if breastfeeding is involved. Soon my son entered this new age of literally digesting world, by eating actual food and by drinking. Words followed that described the food that called to him in the most appealing way like “nana” (banana), “Mus” (almond butter), “Wassa” (Water), “Brot” (bread), and so on. But then he picked up a word which in its meaning fascinates me until this day: “mehr” (more). In the jumble of words, we throw at him every day, how did he discern this very specific word and its meaning for his needs to connect with the world?

What we might learn from children

Staying with my apprehension of endangering him with ideas of our accelerated societies that love machines and want more and more of everything (look out for the irony here), how problematic could this word be? Is this maybe his way of experiencing Rosa’s observation of the worlds Unverfügbarkeit, i.e. uncontrollability, as a necessary relational quality of life by wanting more but sometimes not getting more? Or is it simply his word that enables him to respond, to touch the world back as it confronts him. Is it actually both? Because it is not only more food, it is also more drawing, more running, more cuddling and tickling, more reading, more bath time, more everything. Basically, it is more world that he wants to experience and that is what makes him the expert on resonance. I do not only invite the readers but actually also myself to inhale some bits of this childish and loveable curiosity

that does not follow any deeper meaning than a pure wish for getting in touch with the world, by listening up and by staying open.

“More world, please!” (Picture: Mabel Ramisch)

Author: Mabel Ramisch

If you have any comments or question on the essay, feel warmly invited to contact the author (m.ramisch@ioer.de).

Acknowledgement

The project is supported by the Leibniz Best Minds Competition, Leibniz-Junior Research Group under Grant J76/2019.

